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Research Article

**EVALUATION OF THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN
EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE AND JOB ATTITUDE OF
MANAGERS AND STAFF**Ali Moradi ¹ and Mohammad Hosseinpour*²¹ PhD Student, Department of Educational Administration, Ahvaz Branch, Islamic Azad University, Ahvaz, Iran^{*2} Associate Professor, Department of Educational Administration, Ahvaz Branch, Islamic Azad University, Ahvaz, Iran**Abstract:**

Introduction: The current research was conducted to evaluate the relationship between emotional intelligence and job attitude of managers and staff.

Materials and Methods: The research population included all managers and staff of Petroleum University of Technology in cities of Ahvaz, Abadan, Tehran, and Mahmoudabad. The sample size was determined to be 210 people, who were randomly selected, using Cochran's formula. Data collection tools included emotional intelligence questionnaire and job attitude questionnaire, developed by integrating and localizing standard questionnaires. The normality of the data was also tested using the Kolmogorov-Smirnov technique. Research hypotheses were tested by Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) and structural equation modeling using LISREL software.

Results: The research results revealed that emotional intelligence has a significant relationship with job attitude of managers and staff. Among the dimensions of emotional intelligence (self-awareness, self-management, social awareness, relations management, and emotional intelligence quality), social awareness with the standard factor load of 0.71 had the highest effect on job attitude. In addition, it was found that while emotional intelligence quality with the standard factor load of 0.21 had the lowest effect on job attitude, results of the t-value (t-value) calculation indicate that this relationship is also significant.

Discussion and Conclusion: emotional intelligence quality component was investigated for the first time in this research. The low level of its relationship with job attitude does not mean that it should be overlooked, but it might be correlated with some components of job attitude or other issues related to organizations, which it requires further investigations.

Keywords: Emotional intelligence, Job attitude, Managers and Staff, Emotional Intelligence quality.

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INTRODUCTION:

Many definitions and social services have been changed or move toward fundamental development with introduction of computers, smart phones, and social networks to human life, and accordingly, expansion of Internet. The impacts of these developments and changes in human life become increasingly evident (1, 2, 3, 4). These developments have also changed the learning and study methods of students (5). In today's ever-changing world, where organizations compete with each other increasingly, a major part of the organization energy is spent on its human resources, since it has realized that the people in the organization are the main factor in organizations, helping them to stay in the competition arena. Leading organizations have paid attention to human resources in recent years (6, 7, 8). Nowadays, individual activities are reducing and the importance of teamwork is increasing in organizations. For this reason, communications and relationships between staff and managers have increased, and this has developed new management approaches, which their importance become increasingly evident (9). Organizational leaders require multi-dimensional intelligence, enabling them to make strategic decisions. Multidimensional intelligence of managers would help the organizations to be balanced, coherent, and dynamic (10).

In addition, it should be accepted that the main function and duty of management is empowerment of staff to provide joint performance through common goals, shared values, developing appropriate structure, and training them in performing the work and showing proper and timely response to changes in the organization. However, this concept and meaning of the duty and role has been also changed (11). Based on the conducted studies and UNESCO World Organization, the first university in the world was founded more than 1700 years age in Iran (12-13). Many elites are attracted by Iran universities annually to continue their studies (14-15-16) or to be recruited as faculty members of universities in Iran (17-18-19). Universities are the place for training specialized and committed human forces in the different fields of study (20, 21, 22). In developmental process of human resource management, especially in the 1980s, experts have distinguished two concepts, including human resource management and staff department management. The most important responsibility of management in each organization is management of human resources and managers at all levels of organization, so human resources management is considered as using human resources to achieve organizational goals. However, staff department management is responsible for activities such as employment, compensation, etc. (22). Moreover,

organizational commitment is an effective factor in organizational behavior of staff and organizational productivity (23), and without it, organization cannot achieve success unless the organization members and staff have a kind of commitment and relative effort (24). The dynamic and growing survival of any organization depends on appropriate, timely, and effective decisions, which it would be achieved through intelligence leadership. Managers require wide range of skills to put t organization on the path to excellence and keep it dynamic and lively, and leadership intelligence is one of the key competencies resulting in organizational success (25).

Nowadays, having high-energy, creative, committed staff is considered as one of the most important resources (26). Managers of today's organizations require strong and integrated intelligence in order to adopt coordinated and proper decisions. Managers' intelligence has various types such as organizational intelligence, cognitive intelligence, emotional intelligence, social intelligence, spiritual intelligence, strategic intelligence, and political intelligence, which manager require all of them. One of the most important factors enhancing the level of performance of managers is the interaction and mutual understanding between managers and members of the organization, and the organization leadership should provide the conditions for expressing the emotions and logical reactions in the members. Hence, this research aims to evaluate the relationship between the emotional intelligence and the job attitude of managers and staff at Petroleum University of Technology in Iran.

The job attitudes of staff have a direct or indirect impact on the organization. Thus, investigating the job attitude of staff is required in order to improve their work and efficiency, and several studies have been conducted so far on job attitude or at least its components and dimensions. Results suggest a direct relationship between the staff job attitudes and their effectiveness productivity. Hence, realizing the effective factors and satisfaction level of staff with their jobs has drawn the attention of the researchers. In order to examine the factors affecting the job of staff and managers of Petroleum University of Technology in Iran. (Tehran, Ahvaz, Abadan and Mahmoudabad), we aim to evaluate the relationship between emotional intelligence and job attitude of managers and staff. As intelligence is a type of acquired intelligence, the emotional intelligence capabilities of staff, especially managers and supervisors can be enhanced through required trainings. Considering the importance of emotional intelligence and its relationship with job attitudes of staff, conducting research in this regard is required. Many studies have been conducted in this regard, which they are summarized below:

Neghabi and Bahadori (2011) indicated that the emotional intelligence components have a significant relationship with entrepreneurial behavior of staff. The dimensions of evaluating the feelings of others, the regulation of emotions, and using the emotions had the highest impact on entrepreneurial behavior. The secondary results also showed that entrepreneurial behavior is not significantly different between males and females (27). Jang Hoon and Chihyung (2012) carried out a research in the United States entitled "reducing the job burnout and increasing job satisfaction, the effective role of emotional intelligence and emotional efforts", in which 309 people with academic education working at hotel were assessed. The result showed that emotional intelligence has a positive and direct relationship with job satisfaction and job burnout (28). Ignat and Clipa (2012) conducted a research in the Romania and concluded that teachers with a higher level of emotional intelligent have a more positive attitude towards their job and they are more satisfied with their life (29). Nordin (2012) in research conducted in Malaysia concluded that emotional intelligence had a relationship with job satisfaction, but among the emotional intelligence dimensions, the dimension of emotional recognition to emotional regulation has higher importance (30). Dincer et al. (2011) in a study conducted in Turkey concluded that emotional intelligence has a direct relationship with innovation and initiation of managers.

The reliability coefficient of Cronbach's alpha in this research was obtained 92.5%. Based on analytical theorists, intelligence is the ability to use cryptic phenomena or effective behavior, or adaptation to new situations or recognizing the states and qualities of the environment. The best analytical definition of intelligence has been proposed by American psychologist, named David Wechsler, who argues that intelligence means thinking wisely, rational act, and effective behavior in the environment (Bakhshayesh, 2011). Experts argue that IQ at best state accounts for 20% of life success and 80% of successes depend on factors related to emotional intelligence, and the destiny of people in many cases depends on the skills forming the intelligence emotional intelligence (Mashabaki and Dustdar, 2006). Research institute argues that 12.5 percent of any sum of money earned by human activity results from human wisdom and knowledge and 87.5 percent of it is earned from his ability to get away with people, meaning that:

$$\text{Success production} = 12.5\% \text{ science} + 87.5\% \text{ anthropology}$$

(Soltani, 2010: 216).

For this reason, Resulett stated that the most important element of success in this formula is the way to get away with the people (Amini, 2005). Emotional intelligence is related to capabilities such as communication, recognizing your own and others' strengths and weaknesses and it has particular importance for manager, since it can affect the abilities, such as leadership and staff (Momeni, 2006). In general, emotional intelligence can be defined as using emotional capability in individual and group behavior to achieve maximum outcome with maximum satisfaction (Kiarouji, 2006). Attitude means readiness for a special reaction to a person, thought or position, and in organizational behavior, it is the view expressed on people, things, or events and it indicates the type of one's feelings about it. The importance of attitudes in organizations is due to the impact on staff behavior (Mashabaki and Doustar, 2006). With regard to the subject matter, the main question of this research is whether there is a significant relationship between emotional intelligence and its components and the attitude of managers and staff in Petroleum University of Technology in Iran.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

The current research is applied in terms of objective, since its results are used for the considered population. In terms of data collection, it is a descriptive-survey. Due to the relationship between variables and their components, this research is correlational in terms of the nature and method. In this research, two methods of library and field studies were used to collect data. The research population included all managers and staff of Petroleum University of Technology in Ahwaz, Abadan, Tehran and Mahmoudabad cities. Using Cochran's formula, the sample size was determined 210 people, who were randomly selected. Data collection tools included two questionnaires, including emotional intelligence questionnaire and job attitude questionnaire, developed by integrating and localizing the standard questionnaires. Then, they were analyzed by categorizing them and using descriptive and inferential statistical methods and using spss21 software. As validity of the information is very important and the inertial information prevents the discovery of truth, two principles of accuracy and accuracy and precision are always considered. On the other hand, the normality of the data was tested using

Kolmogorov-Smirnov technique. Research hypotheses were tested using Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) and structural equation modeling through LISREL software.

RESULTS:

In this research, a questionnaire was used to collect data. Thus, confirmatory factor analysis was used to assess the content validity of general structure of the research questionnaires. For the confirmatory factor analysis and modeling structural equations, standard factor load and t-statistics were used. The strength of the relationship between the latent variable and the observed variable is shown by the factor load. The factor load is a value between zero and one. If the factor load is less than 0.3, the relationship is considered weak and it is ignored. The factor load between 0.3 and 0.6 is acceptable, and if it is greater than 0.6, it is very desirable. When the correlation of variables is identified, significance test would be required. The t-test statistic or t-value is used to examine the significance of the relationship between the variables. Since the significance is examined at error level of 0.05 (95% confidence level), if the value of observed factor loads are less than 1.96, the relationship would not be significant. The results obtained from descriptive findings indicate that 67.6% of respondents are male and 32.4% of respondents are female. Thus, the level of female participation in completing the questionnaires was more than that of males. Based on the results, 28 respondents aged less than 30 years, 35 of them aged more than 50 years, and 73 of them aged between 40 and 50 years, and 74 of them aged between 40 and 50 years. Results of the educational level of respondents, 43.3, 9.5, 31.9, 7.1, and 8.1 percent of them had high school, associate,

bachelor, master and PhD degree, respectively. In addition, the percentage of the respondents with the mentioned level of education was 45.53, 10.02, 26.36, 08.06, and 10.02%, respectively.

The results of this comparison suggest appropriate distribution of the questionnaires and the proportion of respondents with different educational levels were close to each other and only respondents with bachelor degree participated more. The results inserted in the table of work experience of respondents also suggest that the highest frequency of the respondents with a total number of 57 (27.1%) had a work experience between 15 and 20 years. Based on the performed test and the final model presented, it could be concluded that emotional intelligence has a positive and significant relationship with job attitude. Based on the calculations performed, the standard factor load of emotional intelligence construct with the job attitude construct was 0.72, indicating that this relationship is very desired and strong. The factor load of t statistics was also obtained 6.37, indicating that the observed correlation is significant. Thus, emotional intelligence has a relationship with job attitude and this relationship is significant. It means that as emotional intelligence of people increases, their job attitude will improve. Accordingly, the person would have more sense of dependency to the organization, act well in the decisions, and more participate in the team work. As a result, he would have more sense of self-esteem and satisfaction with his job.

Table 1: Confirmatory factor analysis and t-value of emotional intelligence

variable	row	Indices	Standard factor load	Statistic T-Value
Self-awareness	1	Adoption of individual disabilities and failures	0.40	5.25
	2	Paying attention to the effect of your own behaviors on others	0.56	7.04
	3	Belief in your own capabilities	0.41	5.40
Self-management	4	To exit from difficult situations	0.42	6.07
	5	Quick adaptation of the changes	0.50	7.36
	6	Paying attention to different solutions before making decision	0.48	7.00
	7	Silence in its proper time	0.58	8.63
	8	Performing regretting actions during irritation	0.35	4.88
	9	Being important for others	0.43	6.16
	10	Tolerating the discouragement without irritation	0.53	7.72
Social awareness	11	Annoying others during nervousness	0.59	8.67
	12	Adopting self-criticism	0.65	9.86
	13	Understanding others' feelings	0.52	7.47
	14	Paying attention to meaning of others in communications	0.70	10.74
	15	Seclusion and being quiet	0.63	9.37
	16	Quick attention to work environment	0.55	7.94
Relations management	17	Problem-solving in difficult situations	0.50	7.08
	18	Getting away with others	0.62	9.05
	19	Clear and effective communication with others	0.43	5.96
	20		0.68	10.26
	21	Paying attention to other party feelings to manage the communication		
	22	Gaining more information to cope with others well	0.64	4.49
Emotional intelligence quality	23	Explaining your own meaning or feeling to others	0.66	9.82
	24	Paying attention to your own and others' feeling	0.58	8.35
	25	Cleverness and intelligence in problem solving	0.69	10.43
	26	Following the experiences rather than logic	0.60	8.70
	27	Evaluating the people excitements and emotions	0.52	9.64
	28	Paying attention to view of others	0.57	8.24
	29	Thinking on view of people and exchanged votes	0.68	10.24
	30	Being determined in executing the decisions	0.61	8.84
		Avoiding frequent changing the decisions	0.61	8.89

Table 2: results of confirmatory factor analysis and t-value of job attitudes

variable	row	Indices	Standard factor load	Statistic T-Value
Job involvement	1	Tendency to perform multiple works simultaneously	0.93	10.80
	2	An effort to perform simultaneous activities	0.91	11.94
	3	Completing the work before starting the next work	0.38	3.56
	4	Simultaneous working on several tasks	0.88	10.54
	5	Spending the maximum effort	0.65	7.31
Job satisfaction	6	Using the skills and capabilities	0.37	6.28
	7	Interest in working in the organization	0.58	8.79
	8	Performing the activity daily	0.29	4.30
	9	Satisfaction with nob tasks	0.55	9.09
	10	Importance of work for organizational success	0.37	6.28
	11	Sense of appropriateness of the work level	0.31	4.11
Organizational commitment	12	Working beyond the duty to help the organization	0.52	7.08
	13	Tendency to stay in organization	0.79	11.25
	14	Lack of interest to other organizations	0.55	6.58
	15	The necessity of staying in this organization	0.41	4.90
	16	Permanent loyalty to the organization	0.25	4.54
	17	Real interest in job and organization	0.60	10.60
	18	High importance of the role in the organization	0.33	4.98
	19	Belief in existence of other organization in the case of leaving this organization	0.39	3.35
Organizational self-esteem	20	Organization reliance on staff	0.69	10.95
	21	Being employed seriously in the organization	0.49	8.16
	22	Being important in the organization	0.82	12.77
	23	being trusted in the organization	0.42	6.73
	24	Being effective and useful in organization	0.33	6.24
Organizational entrepreneurship	25	Working in line with eliminating the bureaucratic acts in the organization	0.39	4.79
	26	Interest in acquiring new skills in organization	0.44	6.59
	27	Quick reducing of timely actions in the case of lack of achieving to expected results	0.36	5.43
	28	Inspiration of colleagues in presenting new practices and methods	0.57	8.14
	29	Creating an environment to make people interested in improving it	0.42	7.40
	30	Organization's support of staff ideas and innovations	0.65	6.78

T-value of results of the final confirmation of the research model

Table 3: Confirmatory factor analysis and significance statistics of relationships among the variables and goodness of fit tests

Relationship	Standard factor load	T statistic	Normal Xi-square	RMSEA
Self-awareness and job attitude	0.63	4.62	2.011	0.42
Self-management and job attitude	0.67	5.79	2.932	0.021
Social awareness and job attitude	0.71	6.25	2.697	0.28
Relations management and job attitude	0.43	6.04	2.970	0.34
Emotional intelligence quality and job attitude	0.21	2.36	2.354	0.018
Emotional intelligence and job attitude	0.72	6.37	2.126	0.037

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION:

Given the great global developments, empowerment of staff is one of the main tasks of organizations (32). The obtained results indicate that the self-awareness component ranks third, while in the research conducted by Cufsius and Zempakis (2007), self-awareness component showed the highest relationship with job satisfaction. In addition, Gerlriuo (2008) concluded that the self-awareness component was not correlated with job satisfaction and organizational commitment, which the result of this research was not in line with the results of stated research. In addition, research results also show that among emotional intelligence dimensions, the level of the relationship between self-management dimension and job attitude ranks second and the component of relations management in terms of correlation with job attitude compared to other components of emotional intelligence ranks fourth. However, in the research conducted by Rezaeian and Keshteghar (2008), the relations management dimension had the highest impact on organizational commitment. The component of emotional intelligence quality was tested for the first time in this research and its low relationship with the job attitude does not mean that it should be ignored, but it might be correlated with some of the components of job attitude or other issues related to the organizations, which it requires to be investigated and tested. As this dimension has been studied and measured for the first time in this research, there is no evidence to compare the results of testing this hypothesis with results of previous studies.

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